

Polar MOSES-Developing cross-compartment strategies investigating the dynamic behaviour of greenhouse gas emissions and influencing factors in arctic environments

Claudia Schütze (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH – UFZ, Department Monitoring and Exploration Technologies (MET), claudia.schuetze@ufz.de)

Uta Ködel (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH – UFZ, Department Monitoring and Exploration Technologies (MET))

Peter Dietrich (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH – UFZ, Department Monitoring and Exploration Technologies (MET))

Martin Schrön (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH – UFZ, Department Monitoring and Exploration Technologies (MET))

Abstract

The dynamics of greenhouse emissions in the Arctic are strongly influenced by global change. For an understanding of the interactions, cross-compartment monitoring approaches will be tested, evaluated and applied within the framework of the Helmholtz cross-centre research infrastructure MOSES. Polar MOSES aims to improve understanding of thaw-driven landscape dynamics and impacts on biogeochemical cycling in permafrost regions and the assessment of permafrost vulnerability to thaw in current and future environments. This will involve observation and projection of thaw-driven dynamics by field measurements and observatories, including the mobile infrastructure of MOSES, remote sensing, and modelling. Within Polar MOSES, mobile OP-FTIR systems are used for the qualitative characterisation of the spatial heterogeneity of greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, geophysical methods such as electromagnetic induction measurements will be used to investigate near-surface structures and processes that influence the dynamics of emissions, and a long-term installation of a CRNS (Cosmic Ray Neutron Sensing) monitoring system will contribute to the evaluation and validation of and validation of satellite-based soil moisture measurements. Therefore, Polar MOSES will significantly contribute to the further development of monitoring approaches applicable under arctic conditions.

1 Context, general objectives of the project, scientific questions

There is still a knowledge gap concerning the spatial and temporal variability of GHG emissions and influencing factors in arctic environments. Especially the development of adapted monitoring methods that link point scale measurements with remote sensing products on the landscape level is still required to address the above-mentioned research gap. An appropriate monitoring design has to face the variable GHG emissions under different environmental conditions, particularly the impact of climate change and severe extreme events on emission behaviour. Due to higher temperatures, longer growing seasons and shorter snow and ice cover periods will arise and affect the carbon cycle of (sub)-arctic ecosystems.

The research infrastructure MOSES (Modular Observation Solutions for Earth Systems) of the Helmholtz Association offers new opportunities to investigate terrestrial and marine systems. It comprises highly flexible and mobile observation modules (Weber et al., 2022; www.moses-helmholtz.de). The infrastructure enables

an approach of event-driven MOSES campaigns to investigate interactions of short-term events and long-term trends across Earth compartments. The system became operational in 2022 and is now ready to use. The main research topics at UFZ and AWI for MOSES are event-driven campaigns to investigate weather extremes (e.g., floods and droughts) and rapid thawing permafrost events.

With the proposed hierarchical, cross-compartment approach, which aims to study greenhouse gas emissions in arctic environments, the following main research questions can be addressed:

- A. What are the contributions of each compartment to the landscape-level GHG fluxes?
- B. Do the GHG fluxes of the different compartments show similar responses to varying meteorological and near-surface conditions?
- C. What are the main controlling factors for landscape-level GHG fluxes?

The investigations of GHG concentrations and fluxes will be carried out in relation to relevant environmental factors, such as atmospheric, terrestrial near-surface, and shallow water conditions. The expected research results will help to understand how sensitive the GHG fluxes of the different compartments (terrestrial and aquatic systems) react to changes in environmental conditions and how this is reflected in the exchange on the landscape scale.

2 State of the Art

Methane (CH₄) is considered a climate-changing trace gas that is emitted in large quantities (about 600 Tg CH₄ per year) from both natural and anthropogenic sources (Crutzen & Lelieveld, 2001). Its atmospheric mixing ratio has increased more than two-fold since pre-industrial, contributing approx. 20% of the radiative climate forcing for all greenhouse gases (Hamdan & Wickland, 2016). The arctic environment, with its marine systems and permafrost soils, is also considered a net source of CH₄ to the atmosphere. However, the total emission per year is a highly uncertain term in the natural atmospheric methane budget. Possible primary sources of CH₄ include: (1) leaks from geological marine seepage; (2) production from sediments or thawing (sub-sea) permafrost layers; (3) emission from the destabilisation of marine hydrates; (4) in situ production in soils and the water column (USEPA, 2010). In particular, summing biogenic, geological, and hydrate emissions from oceans leads to an oceanic methane emission range of roughly 6 - 12 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (Weber et al., 2019). However, the global flux from marine environments is dominated by shallow near-shore environments, where CH₄ released from the seafloor can escape to the atmosphere before oxidation. Permafrost thaw events occur due to warming and wetting of the surface and have the potential to release gas on very short time scales. The permafrost soils in the Arctic store about 10x10¹¹ T of organic carbon in the top 0–3 m; 3x10¹¹ T more compared to the average of carbon in the atmosphere within the period 2010-2019 (Linderoth et al., 2022, Friedlingstein et al., 2020, Hugelius et al., 2014). However, there is significant uncertainty regarding the timing and magnitude of potential feedback caused by global warming (Myers-Smith et al., 2020).

Abiotic and biotic conditions such as air temperature, soil moisture, active layer depth, and vegetation are the most controlling factors in explaining the variation in ecosystem respiration (CO₂) and CH₄ emissions in arctic regions (Linderoth et al., 2022). In particular, soil moisture is one of the main controlling factors for soil gas emissions. Changes in soil moisture influence the water availability to vegetation and soil ecological processes like carbon and nutrient cycling, impacting environmental systems and processes like greenhouse gas emissions, leaching, etc. While traditional

soil moisture measurements are done using point-based methods, the recent development of cosmic-ray neutron sensing (CRNS) offers the opportunity to measure the fluid soil water content at the field scale. The **CO**smic-ray **S**oil Moisture **O**bserving **S**ystem (COSMOS) provides averaged soil moisture time series at more than 100 stationary observatories (Zreda et al. 2012, Bogena et al. 2022). Satellite soil moisture products such as Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) or Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) can be evaluated and validated with the in-situ soil moisture data from CRNS stations. A cosmic ray station in Svalbard would be a unique extension of COSMOS.

In order to obtain a comprehensive picture of the processes and their impacts on the environmental systems, a cross-compartment (water, atmosphere and soil) investigation of GHG emissions and their interacting controlling factors is required to allow the assessment of the resulting CO₂ and CH₄ emissions. This approach has already been applied in several MOSES campaigns (Boike and Dallimore, 2020; Bussmann et al. 2021, 2022; Kunz et al., 2022) and has to be further developed and adapted to Arctic regions.

3 Methodology

The main focus of the planned campaigns is targeted at the comparison of near-shore terrestrial and marine fluxes in arctic environments. That implies the investigation of near-surface to atmosphere exchange processes. The investigations will be aimed at applying and validating a near-surface monitoring concept covering different scales to enable reliable estimation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission sources and rates.

The long-term observatory in Ny-Ålesund and its ideal location for arctic research and environmental monitoring offer excellent conditions to address our main research topics:

1. compare terrestrial and aquatic CO₂ and CH₄ emission patterns (ambient concentrations, fluxes) and study the compartmental interactions under arctic conditions
2. investigate relevant abiotic / meteorological controls of the emission processes (e.g., air and water temperature, humidity and air pressure conditions, near-surface characteristics such as soil moisture as a main terrestrial control factor at the atmospheric boundary
3. Deploy a set of harmonised and multi-disciplinary methods in order to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the emission processes and the related cross-compartment impacts
4. compare various measurement techniques and devices in terms of an inter-comparison for investigations under arctic conditions in accordance with the MOSES philosophy considering the technical aspects for an optimal monitoring design, as well as development and evaluation of standard operating procedures.

In the Polar MOSES project, we want to support the further development of reliable greenhouse gas monitoring by linking satellite measurements with ground-based investigations. In the case of ground-based measurements, a distinction must be made between methods for monitoring greenhouse gases (OP-FTIR) and methods for observing environmental variables that influence the intensity of greenhouse gas fluxes (CRNS for soil moisture monitoring). One of the foci of that proposal is primarily targeted at the activities in Svalbard to provide essential data for validating remote sensing products such as the EnMAP hyperspectral satellite mission (Environmental Mapping Analysis Program) and the future **M**ethane **R**emote Sensing **L**IDAR Mission

(MERLIN).

Within the project geophysical measurements (e.g., electromagnetic induction methods - EMI) for fast mapping of spatial soil heterogeneities of the permafrost as influencing factors for GHG emissions as well as the investigation of spatial and seasonal dynamics in soil-moisture conditions (based on CRNS monitoring) are to be carried out. The results of these investigations will support a better understanding of the dynamics of greenhouse gas emissions in Arctic regions.

3.1 Methods applied in 2023**OP-FTIR spectroscopy targeting spatial heterogeneity of GHG emissions:**

An essential pre-requisite for the secured valorisation of remote sensing data and derived value-added data products are in-situ observation data providing information on the structural and substantial environmental situation. In the project, we will use a ground-based remote sensing method – OP-FTIR spectroscopy- which is proven to be a flexible long-path technique for the characterization of larger areas. This method is able to simultaneously detect various volatile atmospheric compounds relevant for environmental assessment with a single rapid measurement. Many greenhouse gas molecules (e.g., CO₂, H₂O, CH₄) have unique signatures (absorption or emission bands) in the measured spectral IR range. IR spectroscopy allows spatial and non-invasive characterization of emissions (Schütze et al., 2013) and is a useful method to capture emissions along the coastline, both seaward and landward.

Compared to already active projects in Ny-Ålesund (RiS 6047, 11780), which are using stationary high-resolution FTIR devices retrieving the dynamics of the total column concentrations of trace gases in the atmosphere performed routinely as part of the NDACC network, we want to apply the passive technique in a mobile mode to obtain IR spectra at different relevant locations. In order to investigate the near surface atmospheric composition, the mobile passive OP-FTIR spectroscopic scanning measurements will be executed with Bruker RAPID devices to cover marine and terrestrial areas. The RAPID passive detection systems can be deployed for 360° remote sensing of threats at distances up to 5000 m. The main advantage of these passive spectrometers is their mobile and scanning operation options allowing a stand-alone deployment also in rough terrain such as arctic areas. Detailed experiments revealed that the uncertainty in concentration determination is mainly depending on the signal amplitude which is a function of the difference between background temperature and target compound temperature (Ziemann et al. 2017). For concentration quantification the authors defined a minimum of 2K temperature difference for sufficient data quality. In the first step we are interested in the qualitative interpretation of spectra to identify emission sources and characterise the heterogeneous emission pattern by directly comparing the different compartments under consideration and their interactions.

Geophysical methods targeting subsurface heterogeneities:

The GHG emission behaviour is also closely linked to the characteristic of spatial distribution of the soil properties (Sauer et al., 2014). In the case of arctic regions the permafrost soil characteristics and here especially the active layer with its dynamic annual thawing and freezing cycles plays the driving role. Existing borehole installations at the Bayelva site and former geophysical investigations by Westermann et al. (2010) provided detailed insights in the permafrost characteristics and the distribution of the active layer. At selected sites we will apply electromagnetic induction methods (EMI) for a rapid mapping of larger areas and profiles. This should allow the identification and characterization of structures that may cause GHG emission

heterogeneities. For detailed investigations of single features, DC geoelectrics will be carried out.

Cosmic ray neutron sensing (CRNS) method targeting soil moisture dynamics: CRNS estimates the area-average water content by counting the cosmic ray neutrons in the air with a horizontal footprint of hundreds of meters and a vertical footprint of tens of centimeters in the soil (Köhli et al., 2015). Hence, it helps close the scaling gap between ground-based point measurements and satellite-derived remote sensing data products (e.g., SMOS, SMAP sensors, Andreasen et al., 2017). With a stationary installation of CRNS detectors, time series of temporal soil moisture variability in the footprint area can be obtained (Zreda et al., 2012, Desilets et al., 2010). It is planned to install a stationary CRNS detector system as part of the permafrost observatory investigating the seasonal dynamics of the cryo-hydro-meteorological conditions. Furthermore, the monitoring of neutron energy spectra with Bonner spheres spectrometers in Ny-Ålesund (RiS 3211) (Rühm et al., 2009) opens new opportunities in terms of further development of the emerging CRNS field technology considering QA/QC, validation and sensitivity.

3.2 Working Packages 2023

We plan several elaborated measurement campaigns in the following years, including setting up low-maintenance experiments with long-term observation options in remote-controlled operations. The fieldwork during the campaigns will be divided into four work packages according to the above-mentioned research topics.

Table 1: Overview of proposed work packages, their compartments under consideration and dependencies /interactions /potential supporting collaborations to other activities/projects at Ny-Ålesund (RiS).

WP	Method	Marine	Terrestrial	Collaboration with WP	Supporting external data/targeted collaboration
1	Mobile OP-FTIR spectroscopy	x	x	4	AWIPEV atmosphere observatory (RiS Project 6817, 2350, 6047, 11780), AWIPEV-COSYNA underwater observatory (KOL07, RiS Project 5742)
2	CRNS		x	1, 3, 4	AWIPEV atmosphere observatory (RiS Project 6817, 10523); Neutron irrigation measurements (RiS 3211)
3	Geophysics		x	2, 4	BAYELVA permafrost observatory (KOL11, RiS Project 2950)
4	Meteorological variables	x	x	Supporting WP for 1,2,3	AWIPEV atmosphere observatory (RiS Project 6817); AWIPEV-COSINA underwater observatory (KOL07, RiS Project 5742)

3.4 Specific goals and timetable for 2023 The proposed work is planned in close cooperation with running projects on the one hand to use existing data (see Tab.1, e.g., meteorology data, energy balance components and subsurface observations available for the last 20 years, Boike et al. 2018) and on the other hand to provide beneficial new data. All work packages are oriented towards long-term observations at least for the

next three years, including the coverage of seasonal variability of the targeted variables. In particular, the CRNS installation is planned to be developed into a long-term station for the next decades.

For the upcoming season, we plan one campaign in the summer with the followings tasks (Tab.2) to lay the foundation for the following years:

Table 2: Planned tasks in summer 2023 for the different work packages.

WP	Tasks	Locations
WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> mobile OP-FTIR spectrometer deployment (Bruker RAPID spectrometer) at selected locations covering different emission and background scenarios, proof of concept 	Ny-Ålesund, harbour region, shore line, airport and Kolhaugen
WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long-term CRNS station: preparation, installation of the detector system manufactured by Hydroinnova LLC (Albuquerque, NM, USA). and integration into data network for real-time data availability Accompanying soil moisture sampling and laboratory determination of soil moisture content with gravimetric method 	Preferred place for installation - AWIPEV Eddy covariance site at the south-western border of Ny-Ålesund
WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMI measurement with subsurface investigation depths from 0.3 m to 1.5 m performed by Geonics EM38 devices 	CRNS site and Bayelva site in consultation with J. Boike (AWI)
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accompanying meteorological measurements for WP1-3: Air temperature, air pressure, RH, based on a digital weather station 	At OP-FTIR measurement points, at CRNS site

4 References

- Alfred-Wegener Institut (AWI), Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar-und Meeresforschung (2022). Long-Term Observations Bayelva. 2022. – <https://www.awi.de/forschung/geowissenschaften/permafrostforschung/permafrost-langzeitobservatorien/lto-bayelva.html>, Last accessed on 2022-09-25
- Bogena, H.R., Schrön, M., Jakobi, J., Ney, P.; Zacharias, S., Andreasen, M., Baatz, R., Boorman, D., Duygu, M.B., Eguibar-Galán, M.A.; Fersch, B.; Franke, T.; Geris, J.; González Sanchis, M.; Kerr, Y.; Korf, T.; Mengistu, Z.; Mialon, A., Nasta, P., Nitychoruk, J., Pisinaras, V., Rasche, D., Rosolem, R., Said, H., Schattan, P., Zreda, M., Achleitner, S., Albertosa-Hernández, E., Akyürek, Z., Blume, T., del Campo, A., Canone, D., Dimitrova-Petrova, K., Evans, J.G., Ferraris, S., Frances, F., Gisolo, D., Güntner, A., Herrmann, F., Iwema, J., Jensen, K.H., Kunstmann, H., Lidón, A., Looms, M.C., Oswald, S., Panagopoulos, A., Patil, A., Power, D., Rebmann, C., Romano, N., Scheffele, L., Seneviratne, S., Weltin, G., Vereecken, H. (2022). COSMOS-Europe: a European network of cosmic-ray neutron soil moisture sensors. *Earth System Science Data* 14 (3), 1125 – 1151. <https://doi.org/10.34731/x9s3-kr48>
- Bogena, H.R., Herrmann F., Jakobi, J., Brogi, C., Ilias, A., Huisman, J.A., Panagopoulos, A. and Pisinaras, V. (2020). Monitoring of Snowpack Dynamics With Cosmic-Ray Neutron Probes: A Comparison of Four Conversion Methods. *Front. Water* 2:19. doi: 10.3389/frwa.2020.00019
- Bussmann, I., Brix, H., Flöser, G., Ködel, U., and Fischer, P. (2021). Detailed Patterns of Methane Distribution in the German Bight, *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.728308>
- Bussmann, I., Koedel, U., Schütze, C., Kamjunke, N., Koschorreck, M. (2022). Spatial variability and hotspots of methane concentrations in a large temperate river. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 10, art. 833936, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.833936>
- Crutzen, P.J. & Lelieveld, J. (2001). Human Impacts on atmospheric chemistry. In: *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Science* 29 (2001), 178-45
- Desilets, D., Zreda, M. & Ferré, T. P. A. Nature's neutron probe (2010). Land surface hydrology at an elusive scale with cosmic rays. *Water Resour Res* 46

Friedlingstein, P., O'Sullivan, M., Jones, M. W., Andrew, R. M., Hauck, J., Olsen, A., Peters, G. P., Peters, W., Pongratz, J., Sitch, S., Le Quére, C., Canadell, J. G., Ciais, P., Jackson, R. B., Alin, S., Aragão, L. E. O. C., Arneth, A., Arora, V., Bates, N. R., Becker, M., Benoit-Cattin, A., Bittig, H. C., Bopp, L., Bultan, S., Chandra, N., Chevallier, F., Chini, L. P., Evans, W., Florentie, L., Forster, P. M., Gasser, T., Gehlen, M., Gilfillan, D., Gkritzalis, T., Gregor, L., Gruber, N., Harris, I., Hartung, K., Haverd, V., Houghton, R. A., Ilyina, T., Jain, A. K., Joetzjer, E., Kadono, K., Kato, E., Kitidis, V., Korsbakken, J. I., Landschützer, P., Lefèvre, N., Lenton, A., Lienert, S., Liu, Z., Lombardozzi, D., Marland, G., Metzl, N., Munro, D. R., Nabel, J. E. M. S., Nakaoka, S.-I., Niwa, Y., O'Brien, K., Ono, T., Palmer, P. I., Pierrot, D., Poulter, B., Resplandy, L., Robertson, E., Rödenbeck, C., Schwinger, J., Séférian, R., Skjelvan, I., Smith, A. J. P., Sutton, A. J., Tanhua, T., Tans, P. P., Tian, H., Tilbrook, B., van der Werf, G., Vuichard, N., Walker, A. P., Wanninkhof, R., Watson, A. J., Willis, D., Wiltshire, A. J., Yuan, W., Yue, X., and Zaehle, S. (2020). Global Carbon Budget 2020, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 3269–3340, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-3269-2020>.

Hamdan, L. J. & Wickland, K. P. (2016). Methane emissions from oceans, coasts, and freshwater habitats: New perspectives and feedbacks on climate. In: *Limnology and Oceanography* 61 (2016), Nr. S1, S3-S12. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.10449>.

Hugelius, G., Strauss, J., Zubrzycki, S., Harden, J. W., Schuur, E. A. G., Ping, C.-L., Schirmer, L., Grosse, G., Michaelson, G. J., Koven, C. D., O'Donnell, J. A., Elberling, B., Mishra, U., Camill, P., Yu, Z., Palmtag, J., and Kuhry, P. (2014). Estimated stocks of circumpolar permafrost carbon with quantified uncertainty ranges and identified data gaps, *Biogeosciences*, 11, 6573–6593, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-6573-2014>.

Kawasaki, K., Osterkamp, T.E. (1988). Mapping shallow permafrost by electromagnetic induction — Practical considerations, *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, Volume 15, Issue 3, 1988, 279-288, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-232X\(88\)90074-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-232X(88)90074-2).

Kunz M, Abbas S, Bauckholt M, Böhmländer A, Feuerle T, Gasch P, Glaser C, Groß J, Hajnsek I, Handwerker J, Hase F, Khordakova D, Knippertz P, Kohler M, Lange D, Latt M, Laube J, Martin L, Mauder M, Möhler O, Mohr S, Reitter RW, Rettenmeier A, Rolf C, Saathoff H, Schrön M, Schütze C, Spahr S, Späth F, Vogel F, Völksch I, Weber U, Wieser A, Wilhelm J, Zhang H, Dietrich P (2022). Swabian MOSES 2021: An interdisciplinary field campaign for investigating convective storms and their event chains. *Front. Earth Sci.* 10:999593. doi: 10.3389/feart.2022.999593

Lindroth, A., Pirk, N., Jónsdóttir, I. S., Stiegler, C., Klemmedsson, L., and Nilsson, M. B.: CO₂ and CH₄ exchanges between moist moss tundra and atmosphere on Kapp Linné, Svalbard, *Biogeosciences*, 19, 3921–3934, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-19-3921-2022>, 2022.

Myers-Smith, I. H., Kerby, J. T., Phoenix, G. K., Bjerke, J. W., Epstein, H. E., Assman, J. J., John, C., Adreu-Hayles, L., Angers-Blondin, S., Beck, P. S. A., Berner, L. T., Bhatt, U. S., Bjorkman, A. D., Blok, D., Bryn, A., Christiansen, C. T., Cornelissen, J. H. C., Cunliffe, A. M., Elmendorf, S. C., Forbes, B. C., Goetz, S. J., Hollister, R. D., de Jong, R., Loranty, M. M., Marcias-Fauria, K., Maseyk, K., Normand, S., Olofsson, J., Parker, T. C., Parmentier, F.-J. W., Post, E., Schaepman-Strub, G., Stordal, F., Sullivan, P. F., Thomas, H. J. D., Tømmervik, H., Treharne, R., Tweedie, C. E., Walker, D. A., Wilking, M., and Wipf, S. (2020). Complexity revealed in the greening of the Arctic, *Nat. Clim. Change*, 10, 106–117, 2020.

NY-ÅLESUND RESEARCH STATION NORWAY (2022). Ny-Ålesund Research Station - Home. 2022. – <https://nyalesundresearch.no/>, Last accessed on 2022-09-22

Rühm, W., Mares, V., Pioch, C., Simmer, G., & Weitzenegger, E. (2009). Continuous measurement of secondary neutrons from cosmic radiation at mountain altitudes and close to the North Pole—a discussion in terms of H*(10). *Radiation protection dosimetry*, 136(4), 256-261.

Sauer, U. ; Watanabe, N. ; Singh, A. ; Dietrich, P. ; Kolditz, O. ; Schütze, C. (2014). Joint interpretation of geoelectrical and soil-gas measurements for monitoring CO₂ releases at a natural analogue. *Near Surface Geophysics* 12, Nr. 1, 165-178. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3997/1873-0604.2013052>.

Schütze C, Spahr S, Späth F, Vogel F, Völksch I, Weber U, Wieser A, Wilhelm J, Zhang H and Dietrich P (2022). Swabian MOSES 2021: An interdisciplinary field campaign for investigating convective storms and their event chains. *Front. Earth Sci.* 10:999593. 10.3389/feart.2022.999593

Schattan, P., Köhli, M., Schrön, M., Baroni, G. & Oswald, S. E. (2019). Sensing Area-Average Snow Water Equivalent with Cosmic-Ray Neutrons: The Influence of Fractional Snow Cover. *Water Resour Res* 55, 10796–10812

Schütze, C., Bräuer, K., Dietrich, P., Engnath, V., Gisi, M., Horak, G., Leven, C., Lübber, A., Möller, I., Nierychlo, M., Schlömer, S., Schuck, A., Serfling, U., Simon, A., Streil, T., Sauer, U. (2015). MONACO—Monitoring Approach for Geological CO₂ Storage Sites Using a Hierarchical Observation Concept. In: LIEBSCHER, A. (Hrsg.); MÜNCH, U. (Hrsg.): *Geological Storage of CO₂ – Long Term Security Aspects: GEOTECHNOLOGIEN Science Report No. 22*. Springer International Publishing, 2015, S. 33–57

Schütze, C.; Dietrich, P.; Sauer, U. (2013). Diagnostic Monitoring to identify preferential pathways for CO₂ degassing at the surface: Tools for investigations at different spatial scales validated at a natural analogue site. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 18, 285-295.

USEPA Office of Atmospheric Programs (2010). Methane and Nitrous Oxide Emissions From Natural Sources. In: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency EPA 430-R-10-001 (2010), 194

Vanhala, H., Lintinen, P., Ojala, A. (2009). Electrical Resistivity Study of Permafrost on Ridnitšohkka Fell in Northwest Lapland, Finland, *Geophysica* (2009), 45(1–2), 103–118, https://www.geophysica.fi/pdf/geophysica_2009_45_1-2_103_vanhala.pdf, Last accessed on 2022-09-25

Weber, T., Wisemann, N.A., Kock, A. (2019). Global ocean methane emissions dominated by shallow coastal waters. In: *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019), S. 4584. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-12541-7>.

Westermann, S., Wollschläger, U., Boike, J. (2010). Monitoring of active layer dynamics at a permafrost site on Svalbard using multi-channel ground-penetrating radar. *The Cryosphere* 4, Nr. 4, 475–487. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/tc-4-475-2010>. – DOI 10.5194/tc-4-475-2010.

Ziemann, A., Starke, M., Schütze, C. (2017). Line-averaging measurement methods to estimate the gap in the CO₂ balance closure – possibilities, challenges, and uncertainties. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.* 10 (11), 4165 - 4190

Zreda, M., Shuttleworth, W. J., Zeng, X., Zweck, C., Desilets, D., Franz, T., and Rosolem, R. (2012). COSMOS: the COsmic-ray Soil Moisture Observing System, *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 16, 4079–4099, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-4079-2012>.